

Assessment of Synthetic Turfgrass Dataset Generation for Divot Detection

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Overview

- Motivations
- GrassClover dataset
- Our Turfgrass dataset
 - Blender
 - Grass Modelling
 - Grass Placement
 - Image + Label creation
 - Turfgrass dataset
- Colour Augmentations
 - ST: Source to destination image transfer augmentation
 - AWB: auto-white balance augmentation
- Conclusion

Motivations

- Precision Turfgrass Management (PTM)
 - Reduce environmental impact
 - EU regulations on herbicides
 - Enhance work efficiency
 - Divots on golf courses is the focus

Divot: Piece of turf cut from the ground when a golfer plays a stroke

GrassClover dataset

- Plants cropped (4–8 pixel per mm)
- Soil backgrounds
- Segmentation masks

(a) Unknown clover leaf.
43 samples.

(b) White clover leaf.
37 samples.

(c) White clover
flower.
36 samples.

(d) Red clover
flower.
1 sample.

(e) Red clover.
9 samples.

(f) Red clover leaf.
23 samples.

(g) Grass.
55 samples.

(h) Shepherd's purse.
4 samples.

(i) Thistle.
6 samples.

(j) Dandelion.
16 samples.

GrassClover dataset

Sample Image

Labels

GrassClover dataset

Model	Object Class					
	grass	white clover	red clover	weeds	soil	clover other
DeeplabV3+	0.58	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.54	0.0
PSPNet	0.13	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.18	0.0
FCN8	0.49	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.37	0.0
UNet	0.35	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.17	0.0

Turfgrass dataset: Blender software

Turfgrass dataset: Grass modelling

- Grass texture
- Geometry

Turfgrass dataset: Image + Label creation

Blender compositor

Turfgrass dataset: Synthetic and Real Images

- Synthetic dataset (Training data)

- Top-Down view
- 400x400 pixels
- 4 pixels per mm
- 6510 rgb + mask

- Real dataset (Test data)

- Top-Down view
- Manual annotation
- 4 pixels per mm
- 400x400 pixels
- 3864 rgb + mask

Turfgrass dataset: Real Images

Colour Augmentations: Source to destination image transfer (ST)

Colour augmentation: auto-white balance (AWB)

Source Image

AWB set

Training results of synthetic data

Model	Pixel Accuracy	MIoU	Classes	
			Foliage	Divot
DeeplabV3+	0.97	0.72	0.97	0.46
DeeplabV3+ + ST	0.98	0.81	0.98	0.64
DeeplabV3+ + AWB	0.99	0.82	0.98	0.66
PSPNet	0.95	0.64	0.95	0.34
PSPNet + ST	0.97	0.68	0.97	0.39
PSPNet + AWB	0.97	0.71	0.97	0.45
FCN8	0.97	0.70	0.97	0.44
FCN8 + ST	0.98	0.77	0.98	0.55
FCN8 + AWB	0.98	0.84	0.99	0.68
UNET	0.98	0.79	0.98	0.59
UNET + ST	0.98	0.81	0.98	0.64
UNET + AWB	0.99	0.83	0.98	0.68

Conclusion & Further Research

What was achieved so far

Turfgrass dataset for Precision Turfgrass Management

Next steps

Develop and refine our data generation workflow

Questions ?

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